

IMPROVING STUDENT'S READING SKILLS THROUGH ACTIVITY BASED LEARNING

Gadoev Doston Zokir ugli,
master's degree student, SamSIFL
Abduvaitov Sanjarbek Said ugli,
master's degree student, SamSIFL

Abstract: As a global medium of communication, the importance of English has increased a lot in the present educational contexts. Effective language teaching and learning process need an effective teaching methodology. The current study investigates the benefits of using activity based learning on the development of reading skills.

Key words: reading skills, activity based learning, brainstorming, storytelling

Language refers to a complex system of communication or the ability to learn and use that system. Language is primarily a means of communication. The field that studies language is called linguistics. To determine the number of world languages, it is necessary to make a distinction between language and dialect. Language is an important means of communication and exchange of ideas between people, in society; the main object of study of linguistics; a thing in existence, a set of sound signs that serve events and their reflection in the mind, which are restored as they really are by members of speech and are known and acceptable to everyone within a certain society, as well as a set of rules about how these signs are combined and combined in the process of expressing thoughts. The fact that language is a social phenomenon, the most important means of communication between people and communities has been emphasized by Eastern and Western scientists, poets and thinkers for centuries. When we talk about language of course, we think about skills that they are always one of the main parts of the language. Among skills reading plays an important role in learning and teaching the

language. Reading is a type of independent speech activity related to the perception (reception) and understanding of information encoded by graphic symbols. To be able to read, first of all, is to master the technique of reading, that is, to instantly recognize the visual images of speech units and to voice them in internal or external speech. Any speech unit is an operational unit of perception. Such a unit can be a word, even a syllable or a phrase consisting of two or more words (syntagma), and even a whole complex sentence in the operative unit of perception, the better reading technique and the better the reading technique, the higher the level of comprehension of the text. Activity-based learning describes a range of pedagogical approaches to teaching. Its core premises include the requirement that learning should be based on doing hands-on experiments and activities. Activity-based learning is rooted in the idea that children are active learners rather than passive recipients of information. If children are provided the opportunity to explore on their own and are provided with an optimum learning environment, then learning becomes more joyful and long-lasting. There are two types of reading: extensive and intensive reading. Extensive reading is human happens when you read for fun. This type of reading is language a hand for learners to choose and study according to their own preferences will come. Through extensive reading, language learners improve their reading skills they can get better. This method is a language learner's vocabulary and grammar As it is an effective way to develop competence, teachers have their own it is desirable to involve their students in reading as much as possible. Intensive reading is reading a specific text and learning new words from that text or involves doing grammar exercises and assignments. In this students analyze the text and pay attention to the use of language materials. In intensive reading, some students grasp the idea presented by the main topic tries to get it and can't get it. Some are each is more attentive to the meaning and usage of words and sentences they read with interest. However, the teacher is of both types of students taking into account their interests,

text selection and interesting exercise for children and must make assignments. To the following results through the development of reading skills:

- to understand the general content of the given text;
- fully understand the content of sentences and paragraphs;
- to understand the essence of the given text;
- to strengthen the new word and grammatical topic given in the text;
- development of students' skills of quick reading and information acquisition;
- formation of the ability to recognize different texts.can be achieved:

The Jigsaw Method: The Jigsaw is a commanding approach for learning descriptive resources. It aids teachers and learners to successfully cover a great deal of learning material in relatively little time. It is also a helpful device in overcrowded classrooms. In this activity, learners are distributed equally into a group of four members each. The content/ study material is also distributed into four parts, i.e. each part is assigned to one learner in a group. In this way a “home group” is formed. The instructor should make certain that every learner has adequate resources to learn the concept.

Brainstorming: a speedy and useful method of producing information for later association and reflection. Throughout a brainstorming session, pupils contribute ideas that appear in their minds concerning the idea or subject under conversation. The Venn diagram, Spider Diagram, etc., can be used to record the information and evidence given by the learners. Smoothness and extent are imperative elements of brainstorming. A brainstorming strategy can be conducted separately on a piece of paper or within a group, verbally or on the writing board.

Storytelling: Successful storytelling is one of the main components of any effective lesson, particularly for children. This is an ability which demands high energy, difference in volume, facial expressions, pitch of tone, gestures and even possibly movement of the teacher in front of the class. Some of the important

guidelines needed to be kept in mind when the process of storytelling is in progress:

- The teacher ought to be as active and forceful as possible in order for the learners to focus on the story and stay tuned while comprehending it.
- The process of storytelling ought to be interactive with the teacher engaging the pupils in the strategy.

The list of used literature

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